

BILINGUALISM IN BOBURNAMA

Jurayev Shahriyor Ibodulloevich

Head of the Department of Uzbek Language and Literature,
Samarkand State University of Architecture and Construction (SamDAQU),
Doctor of Philosophy (PhD) in Philological Sciences

***Annotation.** The article highlights how the Turkic-Uzbek and Persian-Tajik peoples have lived together in harmony and friendship since ancient times, particularly from the era of the Baburids to the present day. It examines the skillful use of Persian words in Baburnama and analyzes them by grouping them into categories. The work also presents examples of Persian-Tajik sentences and poems.*

***Keywords:** comparative analysis, lexeme, word formation, prose and poetry, borrowings, lexical layer, artistry, bilingualism, and zullisonayn (mastery of two languages).*

Introduction

Historically, our homeland, located at the bustling crossroads of the Great Silk Road, has been in continuous contact with numerous cultures and languages. These social connections between the two peoples have evolved and strengthened in our era. The history of the peaceful coexistence and friendly relations between the Persian-Tajik and Turkic-Uzbek peoples is deeply rooted and continues to this day. The ties between the two peoples are vividly reflected in artistic creativity, as seen in both Turkic and Persian-Tajik literature.

According to B.G. Gafurov, such closeness between the Tajik and Uzbek peoples began in the 6th century CE [Gafurov, 1952:110]. Even a form of bilingualism developed in these two languages, with the earliest forms of this bilingualism tracing back to the Achaemenid and Kangju states (7th-6th centuries BCE and 3rd-2nd centuries BCE, respectively) [Askarov, 2007: 34, 64, 164-183, 228, 262].

In our era, these social connections have been further perfected and solidified. Thus, the history of the Tajik and Uzbek peoples living together in harmony and their longstanding friendly relations, dating back to ancient times, continues to this day. These connections are also reflected in artistic creativity in both Turkic and Persian-Tajik literature. Through mutual understanding, multifaceted spiritual and educational cooperation has developed, leading to respect and attention between the peoples. Tolerance has always been a key virtue of our national character. During his reign, Zahiriddin Muhammad Babur treated all ethnic groups equally. In one of his decrees, he wrote:

"Let all nations, whether Turk, Tajik, Arab, Ajam, Hindu, or Persian, citizens and soldiers alike, who rely on the kindness of the sovereign, unite in gratitude for our enduring reign, observe the decrees without deviation, and act accordingly. This decree, bearing the great sovereign's signature, was issued in the year 932 AH (1525 CE) on the 24th of Jumada al-Awwal" [Z.M. Babur, 1990:360].

Therefore, there has always been a need for learning multiple languages in our land. It is known from history that our ancestors were multilingual. Great scholars such as Abu Rayhan al-Biruni, Abu Ali ibn Sina (Avicenna), Abu Nasr al-Farabi, Mahmud Kashgari, Alisher Navoi, and Zahiriddin Muhammad Babur mastered and created in multiple languages. For instance, Abu Nasr al-Farabi is reported to have known over 70 languages. In addition, bilingualism and the tradition of creating poetry "like sugar and milk" have been an ancient

custom in our land. The tradition of bilingualism has existed in all regions of the country, including Tashkent, Jizzakh, Kashkadarya, Surkhandarya, Navoi, Fergana, and Andijan. In Baburnama, Babur describes his native Andijan in this way:

"Andijan... its people are Turkic. In the city and market, there is no one who does not speak Turkic. Their speech is as proper as written language" [Z.M. Babur, 145].

The issue of bilingualism is also clearly evident in Baburnama. In this article, we propose studying the Persian-Tajik words in Baburnama by categorizing them as follows:

1. Numerical terms:

"There was a great quantity of gold and silver tools and equipment. The cloth bearers and cannon bearers were countless" [Z.M. Babur, 1990:41].

2. Characteristics and qualities:

"Boysungur Mirza's affection for Tahir Muhammad increased. Boysungur Mirza also liked Khisravshah. The grapes, melons, apples, and pomegranates, in fact, all the fruits, were excellent" [Z.M. Babur, 1990:43].

3. Descriptive circumstances:

"A Friday mosque was built inside the Iron Gate fortress. Stones were mostly brought from Hindustan, and stonemasons worked there... After raiding the Zardak desert, they brought back over one hundred thousand sheep and about three thousand camels... They were in a state of turmoil and confusion about what to do, whether to stay or leave, for several days" [Z.M. Babur, 1990:54].

4. Place names:

"To the south of Samarkand lies the Garden of Plane Trees, near the fortress. To the lower side of Samarkand are the Garden of Winds and the Garden of Paradise" [Z.M. Babur, 1990:44].

In Baburnama, several Persian-Tajik sentences and poems are also included:

*"And with the intention of battle and confrontation, they turned toward the victorious army camp. The warriors of Islam, who are like the trees of the garden of bravery, formed ranks as straight as cypresses. The tips of their helmets, resembling cypress tops, reached the heights of the sun. Their ranks were like the iron-clad 'Alexander's Wall,' their foundations as strong as the prophetic shariah. The steadfastness of their strength was 'as if they were a well-compacted structure,' and their success was in line with 'they are on guidance from their Lord, and they are the successful'" [Z.M. Babur, 1990:203].

Or: From that sentence, Mawlana Shihab derived the chronogram for this verse:

"Humayun was the heir to his kingdom..."

"Separation from you, I knew, would destroy me,

Otherwise, I could have left this city." [Z.M. Babur, 1990:259].

Or: "Kill today, since it is possible to kill,

When fire rises high, the world burns.

Do not let him pull the bowstring,

When an enemy can be pierced by an arrow." [5, 105].

In Baburnama, Persian-Tajik words, phrases, sentences, poems, ghazals, as well as rubaiyat, are used throughout:

"In this breach, there is no anxiety or fear,

As long as it aligns with the will of the king and firm religion.

His banners spread like the wide heavens,

Each letter like the 'Indeed, We have granted victory' verse." [Z.M. Babur, 1990:293].

In conclusion, it is a historical fact that, since ancient times, Uzbek writers have created works in Persian-Tajik, and Tajik writers in Turkic-Uzbek. They have maintained mutual connections and were never indifferent to each other's works. On the contrary, the tradition of writing in two languages has developed as a shared literary heritage. Interestingly, the customs, religion, living conditions, behavior, clothing, appearance, and culture of the two nations are remarkably similar. The comparative interpretation of the materials of these two languages from a linguistic perspective is also an ancient tradition.

REFERENCES

1. Gafurov, B.G. History of the Tajik People. Moscow, 1952.
2. Askarov, A. Ethnogenesis and Ethnic History of the Uzbek People. Tashkent: University, 2007.
3. Zahiriddin Muhammad Babur. Baburnama. Tashkent: Yulduzcha, 1990.